

MECHANICAL TESTING OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

A large number of publications have been made on the mechanical properties of CFRMs (Continuous Fibre Reinforced Metals). Particular interest was given on two testing routes, bending and tensile tests. This paper compares these testing methods and discuss the influence of the specimen geometry. Tests samples have been produced by a precision casting process employing two different aluminium matrix alloys and a 50% reinforcement with alumina-silica continuous fibres. Flexural strength values have been measured that are at least 30% higher as compared to the corresponding ultimate tensile strength. Depending on the matrix alloy used, significant differences in the plastic deformation of the composites have been observed. Furthermore, it has been shown that the test specimen geometry has a strong influence on strength results. With varying test specimen diameter, differences of up to 25% have been measured.

INTRODUCTION

At the Aachen Foundry Institute a new manufacture route for continuous fibre reinforced metals, based on the investment casting process, has been developed [1]. This process combines conventional investment casting with filament winding technologies, known from the production of polymer matrix composites, and allows manufacture of complex castings with a selective fibre reinforcement. The investigations actually concentrate on aluminium alloys as matrices. For evaluation of the manufactured composites, a number of mechanical testing methods are available. Due to missing standards, however, considerable differences e.g. in strength values have been noticed. A more detailed investigation of the characteristics of the different test methods and the influence of specimen geometries seems to be necessary.

A large number of publications have been made on the mechanical properties of CFRMs, however, very often are both, test specimen geometry and testing conditions, not further explained. Comparisons between different sources are rather difficult. Further investigations should be guided by the objective to develop precise, but simple test methods which allow a representative characterisation of the material. The paper will give an overview on different mechanical test methods and specimen geometries, and will compare and discuss the results.

MATERIALS EMPLOYED

The investigations have been carried out with two aluminium alloy matrices, Al-2%Zn as a weak and Al-5%Zn-1%Mg as a strong matrix. For reinforcement, 50 vol.% continuous-fibres (type Sumitomo Altex) composed of 85% Al₂O₃ and 15% SiO₂, were used. **Table 1** shows properties

of the materials employed. Specimens were cast and tested in the as cast conditions after machining with diamond or hard metal cutting tools to their final geometry.

Table 1: Properties of the Altex fibres and the aluminium matrix alloys used [2, 3, 4].

		UTS [MPa]	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Density [g/cm^3]
Fibre	Sumitomo Altex	1800	210	3.30
Weak Matrix	Al-2%Zn	≈ 102	71	2.79
Strong Matrix	Al-5%Zn-1%Mg	≈ 260	71 - 74	2.91

TESTING METHODS

A large number of different properties are used for mechanical characterisation of the mechanical behaviour of engineering materials, such as UTS (Ultimate Tensile Strength), TYS (Tensile Yield Strength), flexural strength, shear strength, elastic modulus. Depending on the fracture behaviour of the materials the different test methods are more or less suitable. Ceramic materials are primarily tested in bending tests with flat bars. In contrast, the strength of metals is generally measured by tensile tests with cylindrical or flat specimens. For continuous fibre MMCs, as a combination of ceramics and metals, results of both test methods are published in the international literature, however, with a preference on flexural test results.

THE BENDING TEST

Two types of bending tests are known, the three- and the four-point bending test. Due to its simplicity in handling and interpretation of test results, the three-point bending test is advantageous if only flexural strength is of interest. The four-point bending test has the advantage of a constant bending moment within the two inner blades of the test device allowing additionally an easy measurement of the elastic modulus with strain gauges. **Figure 1** shows the features of the four-point bending test. The load is introduced into the specimen at two outer and two inner points of support, respectively, and deflection can be measured with an inductive displacement pickup in the centre of the test device. The resulting bending moment is given in eqn. 1. Between the inner

Fig.1: Schematic drawing of a four-point bending test device with resulting bending moment and load distribution within the specimen (Own investigations: $A = 35mm$ and $B = 10mm$).

points of support a constant tensile stress field in X-axis builds up within the specimen. Assuming a linear stress-strain behaviour until fracture, eqn 2 can be derived. From eqn 1 and 2 follows eqn 3 which allows calculation of flexural strength from the introduced load F (in three-point bending test B can be set as 0).

$$M_B = \frac{F}{4} (A - B) \quad (1)$$

$$M_B = \frac{\sigma_B}{6} * W * H^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_B = \frac{3}{2} * F * \frac{A - B}{W * H^2} \quad (3)$$

Due to the brittleness the above made assumption is valid also for unidirectionally reinforced metal matrix composites, however, only for loads applied longitudinally to the fibre direction. Transverse to the fibre orientation the materials behaviour is dominated by the matrix which allows a certain degree of plastic deformation. Therefore, the assumption of a linear deflection can not be made as described and flexural strength can not be calculated accurately.

THE TENSILE TEST

Tensile tests are usually carried out on servohydraulic testing machines. The specimens have either a cylindrical dog-bone or a flat geometry. Specimen dimensions such as diameter or cross area, length and transition radius are usually determined in international standards, depending on the characteristic behaviour of the material. For continuous fibre MMCs, however, standards are not available and many different types of specimens have been used until now. For comparison of results particular interest has to be given on the geometry of the specimens. **Figure 2** shows a tensile test machine with clamping grip heads. Within the measurement length the stress distribution should be constant over the cross section. The tension can be calculated from the drawing stress, measured with a load cell, and the specimen geometry (for cylindrical specimens eqn 4). For ductile materials the reduction of the cross section during testing has to be considered and, therefore, the specimen cross area has to be measured steadily. Continuous fibre reinforced MMCs show almost no constriction if the load is applied in fibre direction.

Fig.2: Schematic drawing of a servohydraulic testing machine with resulting stress distribution σ_T .

$$\sigma_T = \frac{F}{A} = F \frac{4}{d^2 \pi} \tag{4}$$

EXPERIMENTAL: SPECIMEN GEOMETRY

As shown in eqn. 3 the height H of flat bar specimens is of particular importance in bending test. Sheet specimens with two different geometries, 40*6*4 mm and 40*6*5, were produced for 4-point bending tests. The specimens have been cut by diamond tools from larger cast bars.

For tensile tests cylindrical specimen have been used. A total number of 72 specimen with Al-5%Zn-1%Mg matrix have been investigated with at least four specimens of each geometry. Two different types have been machined by turning from cylindrical cast rods with ø8 mm and ø12 mm, reinforced with 50 vol.% Altex fibres (**Fig.3**). Geometry type 1 is similar to the specimens conventionally used for testing of metals, showing a parallel length of 12 mm allowing also the measurement of the elastic modulus. Geometry type 2 has no a parallel length, but is reduced in diameter in the centre of the specimen. Due to the simple shape, specimens of type 2 are easier to produce as compared to type 1. For both geometries a large radius of 25 mm has been used for the transition from the heads to the measurement diameter.

Fig.3: Specimen geometries after machining. The specimen have been produced from initially D = ø12 mm and D = ø8 mm cast cylinders. Geometry type 1 shows a parallel measurement length of 12 mm, type 2 has no parallel length.

Table 2: Listing of specimen geometries tested. In the table the different measurement diameters of the specimens are given, with the accompanying diameter of the grip ends and the specimen type.

	Specimen Type 1	Specimen Type 2
ø 12mm in Grip Ends	ø4, ø5, ø6, ø8 mm	ø3, ø4, ø5, ø6, ø8, ø10 mm
ø 8mm in Grip Ends	ø4, ø5, ø6 mm	ø3, ø4, ø5, ø6 mm

RESULTS

COMPARISON OF BENDING AND TENSILE TEST RESULTS

Figure 4 shows stress-deflection curves of fibre composites with two different matrices, (A) the soft matrix Al-2%Zn and (B) the higher alloyed strong matrix Al-5%Zn-1%Mg. The maximum flexural stress levels of these two materials are quite similar. The fracture behaviour, however, shows significant differences. With the weaker matrix a higher deflection has been measured, obviously caused by plastic deformation of the matrix as a result of high shear stresses. A strong matrix prevents plastic deformation leading to a nearly linear stress-deflection curve until the fracture occurs. This shows, that the above made assumption of a linear stress-strain behaviour for calculation of the flexural strength is correct only for the strong type of matrix alloys. With weak matrices, however, calculated flexural strength values are slightly higher than real values.

Stress-strain curves have been recorded in tensile tests. In contrast to the bending tests, the matrix alloys used do not considerably influence the stress-strain behaviour. Generally two linear stages are detected with elastic moduli of about 115 GPa and 90 MPa. The transition from stage 1 to stage 2 appears at a stress level of about 200 to 300 MPa. The composite with Al-2%Zn matrix reached an average UTS of 654 MPa compared to 749 MPa for the composite with Al-5%Zn-1%Mg matrix. Tensile strength values are generally lower than flexural strength, see **Table 3**. For comparison, a typical stress strain curve of a tensile test is additionally given in **Figure 4** with a deflection recalculated from the elongation.

Fig.4: Stress-deflection curves of fibre composites by the use of (A) soft matrix and (B) strong matrix alloys and 50 vol.% continuous Aلتex-fibre. For comparison a stress-strain curve of a tensile test is given additionally (C).

Table 3: Summary of tensile and flexural strength of different geometries and matrices.

Specimen Geometry	Matrix Alloy	Test	Strength [MPa]			No. of Tests
			Average	Max.	Min.	
□ 40*6*3.5	Al-2%Zn	flex.	962	1016	900	3
□ 40*6*4	Al-5%Zn-1%Mg	flex.	988	1078	888	3
□ 40*6*5	Al-5%Zn-1%Mg	flex	719	911	591	5
∅ 5mm	Al-2%Zn	tens.	654	707	612	3
∅ 5mm.	Al-5%Zn-1%Mg	tens.	749	893	613	16

INFLUENCE OF TEST SPECIMEN GEOMETRY

In *bending tests*, the influence of the specimen height has been investigated. A significant drop of the flexural strength was measured with increasing specimen height. The average drops from 988 MPa with 4mm bars to 719 MPa with 5mm bars (**Table 3**).

In *tensile tests*, the influence of the specimen diameter of both, the grip ends and the measurement length, as well as the shape of the specimens (type 1 and type 2) on the UTS has been investigated. **Figures 5 to 8** show the UTS graphs with the maximum, minimum and average values given. The scatter of results between the different geometries is considerable: the highest average value measured is 741 MPa, the lowest is 454 MPa. In the figures a dependence between measurement diameter and UTS can be realised, however, with differences according to the geometry type. As a general tendency, a maximum in strength has been measured with a medium diameter. For specimens produced with ∅ 12mm grip ends (**Fig. 5 and 6**) the maximum UTS values can be achieved with ∅ 5 mm and ∅ 6 mm, respectively. For higher diameter the UTS values drop. This could be effected by a higher internal stress potential, resulting from the

Fig.5: Dependence of UTS values on the diameter of the measurement length of specimens with the geometry type 1 machined with \varnothing 12 mm grip ends. 50% of the specimens with \varnothing 8 mm failed in the grip ends and not in the measurement length.

Fig.6: Dependence of UTS values on the diameter of the measurement length of specimens with the geometry type 2 machined with \varnothing 12 mm grip ends. Specimens with a diameter of \varnothing 8 mm and more failed in the grip ends.

Fig.7: Dependence of UTS values on the diameter of the measurement length of specimens with the geometry type 1 machined with \varnothing 12 mm grip ends. All specimens with \varnothing 6 mm failed in the grip ends and not in the measurement length.

Fig.8: Dependence of UTS values on the diameter of the measurement length of specimens with the geometry type 2 machined with \varnothing 12 mm grip ends. Some specimens with a diameter of \varnothing 6 mm failed in the grip ends.

CTE mismatch between fibres and matrix. Another possible reason is the location of the fracture, which appeared in specimens with higher diameter preferably in the grip ends. On the other side, with a very small diameter UTS is also reduced. A reason could be found in effect of specimen preparation. **Figure 9** and **10** show the fracture surface near the surface of the specimen. Obviously, a layer of 3 to 5 fibres has been destroyed during machining. These fibres can not contribute to the strength of the specimen resulting in an reduction of the UTS. **Figure 11** shows the relation of a destroyed layer of 60 μm thickness, corresponding to about 3 fibre layers, to the area of the cross section remaining undamaged. For a \varnothing 3mm specimen, e.g., a fraction of about 8% of the cross section is damaged. The drop of UTS with lower diameter can, however, not be detected in specimens with \varnothing 8 mm.

The comparison of results measured with geometry type 1 and type 2 shows no significant differences. With \varnothing 12mm grip ends the UTS values of geometry type 1 with parallel length are, with one exception, slightly higher than of geometry type 2 without parallel length. The small differences indicate a homogenous quality of the composite material. No clear statement is possible on the influence of the diameter of the grip ends, as comparisons of Figures 5 and 7 or 6 and 8, respectively, show.

Fig.9: SEM photograph showing the transition from the fracture to the machined surface

Fig.10: SEM graph showing the transition area under higher magnification. Machining of the specimen destroyed 3 to 5 outer fibre layers.

Fig.11: Relative reduction of the undamaged fibre area of the cross section by consideration of a damaged fibre layer of $\Delta = 60 \mu\text{m}$ thickness in dependence on the measurement diameter.

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The investigations show that the flexural strength of long fibre reinforced aluminium alloys is generally higher than corresponding UTS values. For strong alloys (Al-5%Zn-1%Mg) the average flexural strength values are approx. 30% higher than UTS. With soft matrices (Al-2%Zn) this difference is even higher, approx. 50%. It must be considered, however, that the calculation of flexural strength can correctly be made only for composites with a brittle fracture behaviour. In bending tests the calculated flexural strength is influenced by both, tensile and transverse properties of the materials. For detailed characterisation, tensile tests are therefore more appropriate. On the other hand, flexural tests are easier to perform and suitable to give first information on the fracture mechanism of the material. Even with a brittle reinforcement like ceramic fibers a high plastic deformation is possible transverse to the fibre orientation, if a soft matrix is used.

Depending on the intended purpose, different specimen geometries are most suitable for tensile testing. For highest accuracy, geometry type 2 seems favourable due to the possibility to measure the elastic modulus. However, the influence of the test specimen diameter is significant. For simple tensile tests without measurement of the elastic modulus, geometry type 1 without a parallel length seems to be more appropriate due to its easier production. Advantageous are given especially in early stages of a process or materials development when a large number of specimens have to be produced. A reason for choosing a specimen geometry as small as possible are the high fibre costs of about 600 US\$ / kg. Damages by machining can considerably effect on testing results especially in specimens with a small diameter. Damages can possibly be avoided by polishing with diamond tools. A specimen geometry of type 2 with \varnothing 8 mm grip ends and \varnothing 5 mm measurement diameter seems to be a good compromise between accuracy and productivity.

For continuation and complementation of the own investigations, flat specimens will further be produced and tested in bending as well as tensile tests. The results will be compared with the results received with cylindrical specimens.

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